

The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian)

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Entry tags: Christianity, Early Christianity, Religious Group, Greek, Text, Christian Theology, Christian Traditions, Early Christian Text, Language, Orthodoxy

Gregory of Nazianzus (ca. 329–390), also known as Gregory the Theologian, a 4th-century bishop of Nazianzus in Cappadocia and later archbishop of Constantinople is widely considered the most accomplished rhetorical stylist of the patristic era, with a significant impact on the formation of Trinitarian theology. When Basil of Caesarea (or Basil the Great) passed away on January 1st of 378, Gregory became the prominent spokesman of the Nicene party that accepted the decrees of the Council of Nicaea of 325. He was invited to take charge of the Nicene congregation at Constantinople, a city torn by sectarian strife. His Chapel of the Resurrection (or Anastasia, in Greek) became the scene of the birth of Byzantine Orthodoxy, that is, the post-Nicene theology and practice of most of the Eastern Christianity. Among the sermons that Gregory preached at the Church of Anastasia were his five “Theological Orations”, a striking presentation of trinitarian doctrine. The sermons were preached in the Church of Anastasia between 379 and 381 and have gained for their author the title of “The Theologian”, which he shares with St. John the Evangelist alone. Nazianzen’s cardinal opponents were the followers of Eunomius and Macedonius, and it is almost entirely against them that these five “Orations” on the Godhead of the Word and the Holy Spirit are directed. Gregory’s objective was to maintain the Nicene Faith of the Trinity, the Doctrine that while there is but One Substance or Essence in the Godhead, and by consequence God is in the most absolute sense One, yet God is not Unipersonal, but within this Undivided Unity there are three Self-determining Subjects/Persons, distinguished from one another by special characteristics or personal properties: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. Gregory of Nazianzus decided to fight back the followers of Eunomius, the Anomeans, as well as those of Macedonius, who denied either the Consubstantiality of the Son with the Father, or the perfect Godhead and Personality of the Holy Spirit. His five “Theological Orations” are the fruit of this effort. They consist of “Oration” 27, “Oration” 28 (On Theology), “Oration” 29 (On the Son I), “Oration” 30 (On the Son II) and “Oration” 31 (On the Holy Spirit). “Oration” 27 is in many ways an introduction of Gregory, as much as it is the topic of debate. Gregory is setting out the proper approach to theology to suggest that this is the ideal for which he strives, while the Eunomians, the Anomean party, have not pursued this end, as evidenced by their argumentative nature and their misleading of the faithful. “Oration” 28 could almost be titled “On God the Creator” since a large portion of the speech is given to the meaning of creation in relation to its Creator. But the oration could also be titled “On God the Ineffable” since a foundational principle for any language about God is recognizing the analogical limits of that language. In many ways, the core of Gregory’s argument is that humans may not know the mysterious nature of God except through the gifts of his creation, and creation speaks loudly of its Creator. “Orations” 29 and 30 are at the heart of the theological debate with the Eunomians. The first deals primarily with various logical objections they raise to the full deity of the Son, while the second deals with scriptural exegetical debates. At the heart of the logical rebuttal is the insistence that God the Father’s relationship to God the Son is logical and not-temporal and analogical and not earthly. At the heart of the exegetical rebuttal is the key that passages that exalt Christ refer to his divinity, while those which limit him or lower him refer to his humanity. In speaking of the deity of the Holy Spirit, “Oration” 31 combines approaches that Gregory applied to the Son’s deity in “Orations” 29 and 30. He addresses both the logical objections and the exegetical debates. Herein, Gregory sets out clearly the language of consubstantiality and of three hypostases.

Date Range: 379 CE - 381 CE

Region: Cappadocia.

Region tags: Asia, Central Asia, Anatolia, Anatolia, Byzantium

Cappadocia was the homeland of Gregory of Nazianzus.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: On God and Christ, The Five Theological Orations and Two Letters to Cledonius: St. Gregory of Nazianzus, SVS Press 2002.
- Source 2: Five Theological Orations: Christian Classics Series, 2021.
- Source 3: The five theological orations by Gregory of Nazianzus, ed. James Mason, 1899

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q_NdjITqLcE
- Source 1 Description: Theological Orations By Saint Gregory Of Nazianzus
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.newadvent.org/cathen/07010b.htm>
- Source 1 Description: St. Gregory of Nazianzus-Catholic Encyclopaedia
- Source 2 URL: <https://medium.com/@postmodern.palamite/gregory-of-nazianzus-the-theologian-an-introduction-to-his-life-and-thought-ad5677a40d27>
- Source 2 Description: Paradox and Relationality: An Introduction to the Life and Theology of Gregory of Nazianzus
- Source 3 URL: https://www.academia.edu/44719469/Gregory_Nazianzen_s_Refutation_of_the_Eunomians_in_His_Theological_Orat
- Source 3 Description: Gregory Nazianzen's Refutation of the Eunomians in His Theological Orations, Gideon Lazar

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://catholiclibrary.org/library/view?docId=Synchronized-OR/npnf.000369.gr.html;query=&brand=default>
- Source 1 Description: Gregory of Nazianzus, The Third Theological Oration. On the Son
- Source 2 URL: <https://catholiclibrary.org/library/view?docId=Synchronized-OR/npnf.000367.gr.html;query=&brand=default>
- Source 2 Description: Gregory of Nazianzus, The First Theological Oration. A Preliminary Discourse Against the Eunomians

- Source 3 URL: <https://catholiclibrary.org/library/view?docId=Synchronized-OR/npnf.000368.gr.html;query=;brand=default>
- Source 3 Description: Gregory of Nazianzus, The Second Theological Oration
- Source 1 URL: <https://tspace.library.utoronto.ca/bitstream/1807/36303/1/Gregory%20of%20Nazianzus%20Theological%20Orations.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Five Theological Orations. Translated with an introduction and notes by Stephen Reynolds
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.ewtn.com/catholicism/library/five-theological-orations-11646>
- Source 2 Description: The Five Theological Orations
- Source 3 URL: <https://archive.org/details/thefivetheologic00greguoft>
- Source 3 Description: The five theological orations of Gregory of Nazianzus

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The five "Theological Sermons" were preached in the Church of Anastasia, at Constantinople, between 379 and 381 when Gregory of Nazianzus was Archbishop of the Nicene congregation of Constantinople. The Church of Anastasia was in fact a chapel, since the Great Church of the capital was somewhat occupied by the Arian bishop of Constantinople Demophilus. Furthermore, the Nicene congregation of Constantinople was somewhat oppressed by the imperial patronage of Arianism. Therefore, the estimated number of people who attended Gregory's orations should have been limited.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Although they are five distinct orations, they are regarded however as a single text.

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: Vocabulary, in the sense that Gregory is somewhat establishing a trinitarian terminology.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, Gregory discusses on Or. 27 issues of Christian rhetoric and discusses the problem of electing too quickly Christian orators, for these latter are not so well trained, both in matters of theology and rhetoric expertise.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Nevertheless, at the first "Oration" (Or. 27) Gregory talks about the true conditions for theological study, painting a portrait of the Christian philosopher.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Yes

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Kafrikova, Lenka. "The Fifth Theological Oration of Gregory Nazianzen and the Historical Contingency of Revelation". Turnhout: Brepols, 2015.

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Thomas , Gabrielle. The Image of God in the Theology of Gregory of Nazianzus. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 2019. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108593410>.

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Norris, Frederick. Faith Gives Fullness to Reasoning: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory Nazianzen. Supplements to Vigiliae Christianae, 13. Leiden: Brill, 1990.

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Dumitraşcu, Nicu, ed.. The Ecumenical Legacy of the Cappadocians. Edited by Nicu Dumitraşcu. Palgrave Macmillan US, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-137-50269-8>.

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), McCuckin , John Anthony . St. Gregory of Nazianzus. An Intellectual Biography. Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir's Seminary Press, 2001.

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Beeley, Christopher. Gregory of Nazianzus on the Trinity and the Knowledge of God. New York: Oxford University Press, 2008.

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Beeley, Christopher. Re-reading Gregory of Nazianzus. Essays on History, Theology and Culture. Washington D.C.: Catholic University of America Press, 2012.

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Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Langworthy, Oliver. Gregory of Nazianzus' Soteriological Pneumatology. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2019.

Reference: The Five Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus (The Theologian), Trigg, Joseph . "Knowing God in the Theological Orations of Gregory of Nazianzus: The Heritage of Origen". Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2009.